

Physical Exercise on Brain β -Amyloid Deposition in Patients with Alzheimer's Disease: Preliminary Findings of an Integrative Review and Bibliometric Analysis

Temática: Physical Activity and Health – Pôster

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Resumo

Introduction: Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disease characterised by neuritic plaques and neurofibrillary tangles due to the accumulation of amyloid- β peptide ($A\beta$) in the most affected area of the brain, the medial temporal lobe, and neocortical structures. Animal models of AD indicate that exercise may modify $A\beta$ deposition, tau pathology, and hippocampal atrophy. However, the precise effects of physical exercise on $A\beta$ deposition in humans remain unclear. **Objective:** Review and integrate existing literature to evaluate the effects of physical exercise on brain $A\beta$ deposition in patients with AD. **Methods:** Our study was divided into two parts. Firstly, an integrative review was conducted, followed by a bibliometric analysis. For the integrative review, a thorough search was carried out across three electronic databases, Medline (via PubMed), Web of Science, and Epistemonikos, covering studies published from 2014 to 2024. Specifically, clinical studies investigating the impact of physical exercise interventions on brain $A\beta$ deposition in patients diagnosed with AD were included in this phase. The final analysis focused solely on studies involving experimental interventions in humans. Secondly, a bibliometric analysis was performed to analyse patterns in the literature. **Results:** The search yielded 1,771 studies. However, fewer studies were conducted in humans. Based on an initial analysis, the current findings do not support an effect of exercise on $A\beta$ deposition. Nevertheless, the relatively short intervention periods and type of physical exercise observed in many studies may explain the lack of efficacy. Conversely, the bibliometric analysis showed an increasing trend in studies examining the relationship of physical exercise and $A\beta$ deposition, indicating a growing interest in the field. **Discussion:** The integration of existing literature reveals a complex relationship between physical exercise and brain $A\beta$ deposition. While the evidence does not strongly support a direct effect of exercise on $A\beta$ accumulation, several factors contribute to this outcome. Heterogeneity in study designs, including variations in exercise protocols and participant characteristics, may explain conflicting results. Short intervention periods and differences in assessment methods also influence outcomes. The interplay between exercise and other factors like genetics and lifestyle habits further complicates the relationship. Longitudinal studies with extended follow-up periods are necessary to assess sustained effects. Future studies should address methodological limitations, incorporate diverse populations, and employ longitudinal designs. Exploring alternative outcome measures may provide valuable insights. Understanding exercise's impact on $A\beta$ deposition is vital for targeted interventions to mitigate disease progression and enhance quality of life for AD patients. **Conclusion:** Our study provides preliminary insights; however, the current evidence does not strongly support a direct effect of physical exercise on brain $A\beta$ deposition in AD patients. Nevertheless, the growing interest in this field and the broader benefits of exercise in managing AD symptoms underscore the importance of continued research.

Palavras-chave: Physical Exercise; Alzheimer's Disease; Amyloid- β Peptide; Neuroscience.

Referências bibliográficas básicas:

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